

Did Gerald of Wales record Black Stork *Ciconia nigra* in Ireland in the 1180s?

Andrew J. Tighe^{1,2}

¹ School of Biology and Environmental Science/Earth Institute, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland

² Pwani University, Kilifi, Kenya

Corresponding author: andrew.tighe@ucd.ie

Keywords: Black Stork, native species, Topographia Hibernica, rewilding

In the wake of the Norman invasion of Ireland, the Norman priest and historian Gerald of Wales (Giraldus Cambrensis) visited the island in 1183 and 1185 and later wrote *Topographia Hibernica* (Topography of Ireland), chronicling his journeys around Ireland. Largely written as a propaganda tool in support of the Norman conquest of Ireland, the book is divided into three parts, the topography and nature of Ireland, the wonders and miracles of Ireland, and the inhabitants of the country (O'Meara 1982). The book has faced a lot of criticism due to its hyperbolic claims about the Irish people and their customs, and is widely considered a work of semi-fiction to justify the colonisation (Knight 2001). However, it should be noted that when Gerald writes his detailed accounts about nature in Ireland, he seems to be biologically correct. For example, he notes that there are Badgers *Meles meles* and martens *Martes* in Ireland, but unlike Britain there are no Beavers *Castor fiber*, Polecats *Mustela*

putorius or Moles *Talpa europaea* (O'Meara 1982). He correctly states that female Sparrowhawks *Accipiter nisus* are larger than males, that Pike *Esox lucius*, Perch *Perca fluviatilis*, Roach *Rutilus rutilus* and Gudgeon *Gobio gobio* are not found in Ireland, that there are three fish that are found in Ireland that are not found elsewhere, presumably Pollan *Coregonus pollan*, shad *Alosa* and Arctic Char *Salvelinus alpinus* (which are in fact native to Britain, but found in areas outside Norman control at the time, such as Scotland and Northern Wales, and as such Gerald would not have been familiar with the species) (O'Meara 1982).

Of interest in this paper, he also comments about the storks found in Ireland, saying "Storks are very seldom seen anywhere in Ireland, and when they are, they are black" (O'Meara 1982). We can be confident that he is not talking about Cranes *Grus grus*, as he talks about them separately, noting how they are very numerous in Ireland (O'Meara 1982). He also notes that the storks disappear in winter (believing they spend the winter in the beds of rivers) (O'Meara 1982), which suggests he is at least familiar with storks and not confused with non-migratory herons. The fact that Gerald notes that the storks in Ireland are black, also insinuates he knows storks to be white, as the native storks *Ciconia ciconia* of France (where he lived for thirteen years) and Britain (where they may have also been present) were at the time (Schmölcke & Thomsen, 2024; Serjeantson 2010; O'Meara 1982). Additionally, in a later version of the manuscript, penned by Gerald (O'Meara 1982) and now held in the British Library, a drawing of an Irish stork is included (Figure 1A), which shows a stork with plumage significantly similar to European Black Storks *Ciconia nigra*, including the characteristic red beak and legs, a white underside, and darkly

Figure 1. (A) The drawing of an Irish stork that appears in the version of *Topographia Hibernica* held at the British Library, published circa 1220. Credit: British Library archive, Royal 13 B. VIII, f.9.

(B) A pair of Black Storks in Poland. Credit: Marek Szczepanek, licensed under CC BY-SA 3.0.

coloured neck, back, wings and tail. The browner colour seen on the neck and wings may have been the artist trying to represent the glossy sheen seen on the birds and has now faded on the 800 year old manuscript, or potentially the colouration seen in juveniles who retain brown colouration longer on the neck than the wings which blacken sooner.

Other circumstantial evidence may exist for the previous presence of Black Storks in Irish placenames. The name for a Crane in Irish is “Corr”, and it has been suggested that the prefix “Cor” in Irish placenames suggests a previous association with Cranes (Ó Tuathail, 2016), with at least 1,360 Irish placenames beginning with the prefix “Cor”. However it also suggested that “Corr” referred more generally to Crane-like birds, with “Corr monadh” meaning a Crane, “Corr riasc” meaning a heron, and “Corr bánn” meaning a white stork (D’Arcy, 1999). By the same logic, the Irish name for a Black Stork would be “Corr dubh”. There are at least seventeen townlands in Ireland with the Irish name “An Chorr Dubh” (Corduff in English), which are largely found across Leitrim, Cavan and Monaghan (perhaps reflecting a past habitat range), with the remaining three found in Dublin and Kildare (Placenames Database of Ireland, 2025).

Black Storks are currently rare visitors to Ireland and Britain (National Biodiversity Data Centre 2024; British Trust for Ornithology 2024), but are non-breeding perhaps due to lack of habitat. In Eastern Europe their preferred habitat comprises broadleaf forest with mature oaks (*Quercus*) for nesting, with open sections and wetlands (Banaś *et al.* 2019, Treinys *et al.* 2009). Ireland at the time of the Norman invasion still had extensive oak woodlands, in addition to large open areas (McMahon 2023) and extensive wetlands (O’Sullivan 2007). Modern Black Storks are also known for their shy behaviour and discreet nesting habits (Svensson *et al.* 2022), which could explain why Gerald noted they were seldom seen. Considering that Gerald of Wales was correct about other aspects of Ireland’s flora and fauna (and unlike his accounts of the people, he had no impetus to fabricate these aspects), and considering the accurate drawing present in the later publication, then perhaps this is a valid record of a species not generally considered an Irish native.

Acknowledgements

Thank you to Sarahjane Power who gave me a copy of the translation of *Topographia Hibernica*, and thank you to Paddy Sleeman who recommended I publish this work in *Irish Birds*.

References

- Banaś, J., Zięba, S., Bujoczek, M., & Bujoczek, L. 2019. The impact of different management scenarios on the availability of potential forest habitats for wildlife on a landscape level: the case of the black stork *Ciconia nigra* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Forests* 10: 362.
- British Trust for Ornithology. 2024. Black Stork, <https://www.bto.org/understanding-birds/birdfacts/black-stork>; accessed 13/01/2025.
- D’Arcy, G. 1999. *Ireland’s lost birds*. Four Courts Press, Dublin
- Knight, R. 2001. Werewolves, monsters, and miracles: representing colonial fantasies in Gerald Of Wales’s “Topographia Hibernica”. *Studies in Iconography* 22: 55-86.
- McMahon, P. 2023. *Island of woods, how Ireland lost its forests and how to get them back*. New Island Books, Dublin.
- National Biodiversity Data Centre 2024. Black Stork (*Ciconia nigra*), <https://maps.biodiversityireland.ie/Species/11254>; accessed 13/01/2025.
- O’Meara, J.J. 1982. *The history and topography of Ireland. By Gerald of Wales*. Penguin Books, London.
- O’Sullivan, A. 2007. Exploring past people’s interactions with wetland environments in Ireland. *Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy: Archaeology, Culture, History, Literature* 107: 147-203.
- Ó Tuathail, L. 2016. *Corr Scual*. Crane Notions. Careful Publications, Letterkenny
- Placenames Database of Ireland. <https://www.logainm.ie/>; accessed 13/01/2025.
- Serjeantson, D. 2010. Extinct birds. In T. O’Connor & N. Sykes (eds). *Extinctions and invasions: a social history of British fauna*. pp 146–155. Windgather Press, Oxford.
- Schmölcke, U., & Thomsen, K. M. 2024. Prehistorical and historical occurrence and range dynamic of the Eurasian Spoonbill (*Platalea leucorodia*) and the White Stork (*Ciconia ciconia*) in Europe. *Journal of Ornithology*, 1-12.
- Svensson, L., Mullarney, K., & Zetterström, D. (2022). *Collins Bird Guide* Third Edition. William Collins, Glasgow.
- Treinys, R., Stončius, D., Augutis, D., & Skuja, S. 2009. Breeding habitat of the Black Stork *Ciconia nigra* in Lithuania: implications for conservation planning. *Baltic Forestry* 15: 33-39.

First record of breeding in Ireland by Common Eider *Somateria mollissima*: a correction

Patrick Smiddy

Ballykenneally, Ballymacoda, Co. Cork P25 C861

Corresponding author: patricksmiddy@eircom.net

Keywords: Common Eider, *Somateria mollissima*, Ireland, first breeding, literature correction

The first record of breeding in Ireland by Common Eider *Somateria mollissima* was reported by Robinson (1912) who stated that an un-named friend of his saw two nests, along with the adult birds, ‘on a small island off the coast of County Down ... close to the mainland’. A correction was subsequently made in the publishing journal, *British Birds*, to the effect that the island was in County Donegal, and not in County Down. The eggs were collected from both nests, resulting in a rebuke from the editors, H.F. Witherby, F.C.R.